

On the topic of who is the real Helen of Troy

There are three well known ancient Greeks who say there was a real Helen of Troy and that the real Helen never went to Troy but was in Egypt the whole time.....Herodotus, who many call the father of history, Euripides and Stesichorus

In Herodotus' story, the real Helen of Troy was protected by a king proteus, many believe King Proteus to be Ramses II.....Queen Maathorneferure's husband was Ramses.....Evidence the two are the same include that King Proteus and Ramses share similarities in attributes either in description or in name, including being aged, shapeshifter, prophetizing, sea attributes, they were based both in Memphis, both described as wise, legendary (ie great), prolific builders and notably long in years

Maathorneferures father, Hattusili III, was Suzerain of historic Troy, Wilusa, Iliion.....Also like Helen of Troy, Maathorneferure came from a royal family, she was married to royalty, and her marriage was a diplomatic marriage.....her father fought Piyama Radu in history, and academics, notably Konstantinos Kopanias, have substantiated that Piyama Radu, a historic figure, is the basis for Achilles through their many striking similaritiesshe is from the same region as the origin of the stories, as she came from Anatolia as did Piyama Radu....also, there are scholars who believe the Iliad was a story originating from Anatolians, the wilusiad epic theory, for many reasons, but in brief, because of the detailed information concerning Anatolia in the Iliad, the almost pro Trojan stance of the story and all of the real life contemporary archives that describe the historical war are Anatolian.....Maathorneferures home nation, in fact, was the location of where the ancient records of the real war originate from, Hattusha

The Helen phantom related to in the stories of Herodotus, Euripides and Stesichorus are alluded to in the the epic cycle, i.e. relating to when Menelaus is with the men inside the Trojan horse and he thinks he hears his wife Helen outside the horse while she mimics the voices of the other wives of the other men....In the epic cycle there is an amnesia potion that is given to Helen in Egypt that she gives to Menelaus.....this, also, has similarities to historic events surrounding Maathorneferures family....magical remedies sent from Ramses' court to cure Hattusilis infertile sister.....the locations are the same, Egypt and Anatolia.....the circumstances are the same, potions to cure something tremendously grieving parallel Helen and Menelaus traveling to Egypt and retrieving potions to heal Menelaus

Then there are the many name equivalencies

Both Helen and Maathorneferure are either in quality or in name referred to or implied as radiant, shining or beautiful and both names are associated with the sun, as the god Re, featured in Maathorneferure's name, is the god of the Sun and the name Helen was associated with the Sun in Ancient Greek times.....both women have attributes of beauty associated with themselves that are attributed to them by the Gods, Helen judged to be the most beautiful by Aphrodite and Maathorneferure means beauty of Re, Horus' truth.....Queen Maathorneferure's name essentially means Helen and Helen is Maathorneferure... Horus and truth being highlighted in Maathorneferure's name also alludes to the Iliad, as Horus is syncretic, the Ancient Greeks believed in syncreticism, to Apollo who features heavily in the Iliad and alluded to in the Odyssey.....even more illuminating is that Maathorneferure's Hittite name is Shaushkanu.....this Hittite name holds the same attributes as the three

goddesses who solicit Paris.....the name is derived from a Hittite Goddess, Shaushka, the Hittite goddess of love, war and fertility....These attributes correspond to the Greek goddess of love and fertility Aphrodite, goddess of war Athena, and the Queen of the gods Hera....Hera was also the Goddess of childbirth and therefore associated with fertility

also, the name of Aphrodite, critical to the plot, meant born from foam or therefore the sea or perhaps an allusion being born across the sea, further evidence of a Wilusiad epic....the goddess Aphrodite is thought to originate from the goddesses of the east, Astarte, Innana and more likely and more directly.....Shaushka